

Youth Goals Research Centre

JEAN MONNET MODULE

PROPOSALS FOR ACTION FROM EXPERT

VIEWPOINTS FOR THE YOUTH GOALS

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YOUTH GOALS RESEARCH CENTRE

INTRODUCTION

WHAT ARE THE YOUTH GOALS?

These are the **Youth Goals** defined by the European Union to reflect the concerns and priorities of young people on policy days that impact their lives.

WHAT IS THE YOUTH GOALS RESEARCH CENTER?

It is an organization focused on the study and dissemination of the **Youth Goals**.

WHAT DO WE DO?

We produce research, reports and information materials to promote an understanding of the **Youth Goals**.

TO WHOM IS IT ADDRESSED?

The information is addressed to young people organizations and decision makers interested in youth policy and in the area of youth in Europe.

YOUTH GOAL

#1 CONNECT UE WITH YOUNG PEOPLE

POLITICAL DISAFFECTION

Many European youth perceive that their voice is not properly represented or that their opinions are not taken into account. This fuels political disaffection.

ACTIVE PARTICIPATION

Programs that facilitate active youth participation must be encouraged to strengthen and inspire the future of the European Union.

POLITICAL DIALOGUE

Dialogue should be promoted among representatives of all ages and levels, in order to give a space to youth voices.

GOOD PRACTICE

One example is the European Youth Event (EYE), which brings together European youth.

YOUTH GOAL

#2 GENDER EQUALITY

DISCRIMINATION STRUCTURAL

Inequalities socio-economic inequalities and traditional roles should break down barriers and eliminate stereotypes to end structural discrimination.

GENDER SENSITIVE APPROACH

The objective is to eliminate barriers and empower all people, promoting a gender-sensitive approach.

END OF GENDER VIOLENCE

It is necessary to eliminate all forms of gender-based violence through legislative measures, prevention and support.

GOOD PRACTICE

One example is a European Directive which states the commitment to combat violence against women.

YOUTH GOAL

#3 INCLUSIVE SOCIETIES

RISK OF SOCIAL EXCLUSION

There are risks of poverty and social exclusion that affect young people who suffer precariousness or experience multiple discrimination.

YOUTH INCLUSIVE

The goal is to ensure that all young people, especially those with fewer opportunities, feel included.

LEGAL PROTECTION

It is necessary to protect rights and promote their exercise, especially in educational and labor inclusion.

GOOD PRACTICE

One example is the EU's Urban Agenda which affirms its commitment to migrants and refugees.

YOUTH GOAL

#4 INFORMATION AND CONSTRUCTIVE DIALOGUE

CRITICAL THINKING

Many young people face information overload in the digital environment. Promoting media literacy and critical thinking is key to combat disinformation.

DIALOGUE WITH KEY PLAYERS

It is necessary to generate real spaces where young people can dialogue directly with policy makers to influence decision making.

RELIABLE INFORMATION

Ensuring that youth have access to accurate and diverse information from a variety of sources is fundamental to a democratic society.

GOOD PRACTICE

The EU Youth Dialogue connects young people with political leaders, encouraging active participation.

YOUTH GOAL

#5 MENTAL HEALTH AND WELLNESS

ACCESS TO MENTAL HEALTH

Many young people lack access to services and mental health support. Easy and free access should be ensured.

HEALTH AWARENESS

Promoting awareness of mental health can help generate a positive view of the good.

STIGMA

It is necessary to eliminate the stigma about mental health and create a culture where young people are not afraid to talk about their well-being.

GOOD PRACTICE

One example is the Mental Health Day, to raise awareness about the importance of wellness.

YOUTH GOAL

#6 TO PROMOTE RURAL YOUTH

BARRIERS RURAL

Many young Europeans live in rural areas have more difficulties in accessing employment, education, transportation and housing.

MOBILITY PROGRAMS

Facilitate the participation of young people in international and virtual mobility from the rural areas.

YOUTH INCLUSIVE

It must be ensured that young people, regardless of their origin, gender or ethnicity, have equal opportunities in rural areas.

GOOD PRACTICE

Erasmus+ Rural and Rural Youth Dialogue boost youth participation in the development of rural areas.

YOUTH GOAL

#7 EMPLOYMENT OF QUALITY FOR ALL AND ALL

ACCESS TO EMPLOYMENT

Many young people face difficulties in accessing to quality jobs. Barriers that hinder this transition must be removed.

LABOR RIGHTS

It is essential to ensure that young people are aware of their labor rights and are not exploited at work.

SUPPORT AT WORK

To promote well-being and development by providing support to young people at work.

GOOD PRACTICE

One example is the EU's Youth Guarantee, which seeks to connect young people to the labor market.

YOUTH GOAL

#8 QUALITY LEARNING

SKILLS BASED EDUCATION

Learning outcomes should be based on relevant and useful skills to guide young people towards the future.

SUITABLE SUPPORT

It is essential to provide all young people with suitable support and sufficient time to facilitate their learning.

EDUCATIONAL EQUITY

Access to a quality education must be guaranteed for all and be independent of social and economic factors.

GOOD PRACTICE

One example is the existence of European Centers for Vocational Excellence, which benefit young apprentices.

YOUTH GOAL

#9 SPACES AND PARTICIPATION FOR EVERYONE

SAFE SPACES

Young people need accessible spaces in which to meet, improve their skills and participate in activities.

INCLUSIVE PARTICIPATION

Inclusive and equitable youth participation at all levels of the democratic process should be promoted.

SUITABLE INFRASTRUCTURE

It is essential to invest in youth infrastructures that are accessible, welcoming and sustainable in order to create spaces open to all young people.

GOOD PRACTICE

The high level of youth participation in municipal youth councils in Finland demonstrates how to include young people in local politics.

YOUTH GOAL

#10

A GREEN AND SUSTAINABLE EUROPE

CLIMATE ACTION

Young people play an essential role in climate action. They need to be empowered to promote environmentally friendly decisions and practices.

YOUTH PARTICIPATION

We must guarantee the participation of young people in the design and implementation of sustainable policies, allowing them to influence a truly green Europe

SUSTAINABLE LIFE

To ensure a habitable future, we must encourage sustainable living, offering options such as green transportation and responsible consumption.

GOOD PRACTICE

The European Climate Pact provides European youth with a platform to connect and take action for the climate and the environment.

YOUTH GOAL

#11 EUROPEAN PROGRAMMES AND YOUTH ORGANIZATIONS

PARTICIPATION AND REPRESENTATION

It is essential to support and involve youth organizations so that they truly represent European youth.

EUROPEAN AWARENESS

Strengthening youth programs in a European context is essential to foster greater European awareness and a shared identity.

FINANCING SUFFICIENT

Access to specific and sustainable funding for youth organizations is key to ensuring their independence and effectiveness.

GOOD PRACTICE

Erasmus+ is a key example that promotes youth mobility and supports the development of youth organizations throughout Europe.

EXPERT VOICES FOR YOUTH

Speaker contributions for the *Youth Goals*

PAULO PORTAS

CV:

Paulo Portas was Minister of Foreign Affairs and Deputy Prime Minister of Portugal between 2011 and 2015. He was also Minister of Defence between 2002 and 2005. Dr. Portas was leader of the moderate conservative CDS-PP party for 16 years, MP for 7 legislatures. Member of the Council of State and of the National Defence Council in different periods. He founded Vinciamo Consulting, a strategic advisory and business intelligence company, with activities in America, Africa, Asia and the Gulf.

He teaches "Goeconomics and International Relations" at the MBA of Nova School of Business & Economics and at Universities and Academies in Europe and Asia. He conducts seminars on geopolitical trends for multinational companies. He is also Vice-President of the Portuguese Chamber of Commerce (CCIP), member of the Board of Trustees of the Champalimaud Foundation and Non-Executive Director of Mota-Engil (since January 2023). And "Membre d'Honneur" of L'Académie du Royaume du Maroc (since 2023). Author of the Sunday television programme "Global". Mr Portas speaks and writes fluent Portuguese, English, Spanish, French and Italian.

SUMMARY

"New challenges facing the European Union today in the field of youth"

Paulo Portas highlighted in his talk the crucial importance of having solid indicator measurement systems in place to properly assess the European youth reality in key areas such as employment, education, political participation and social welfare. He underlined the need to establish constant monitoring mechanisms that enable the effective follow-up of implemented youth policies, facilitating timely corrections. Finally, he emphasised the relevance of carrying out rigorous evaluations of the impact of these policies, based on empirical evidence to ensure concrete results and to continuously improve the interventions aimed at European youth.

EXPERT VOICES FOR YOUTH

Speaker contributions for the *Youth Goals*

MAURICIO BITRÁN

CV:

Mr. Bitrán is recognised as a former Deputy Minister of Development for Ontario and currently serves as a professor at the University of Toronto. His distinguished career includes the negotiation of the Free Trade Agreement between Ontario and the European Union, providing a valuable perspective on international relations and economic development.

SUMMARY

"Crossing science, politics and society in these uncertain times"

Maurice Bitrán's talk addressed the need to use scientific evidence, especially statistical and epidemiological evidence, in the formulation of effective public policies. He described various sources of scientific information such as peer-reviewed studies, grey literature and official reports, pointing out the importance of critically assessing the quality of this evidence. He explained types of scientific studies such as in vitro, in vivo, in silico and human studies (clinical cases, epidemiological and randomised clinical trials), highlighting their advantages and limitations. He also emphasised the importance of identifying and minimising experimental errors and biases through appropriate and rigorous designs. Finally, he underlined that the effectiveness of a policy depends not only on its scientific quality, but also on its social acceptability, highlighting the necessary interaction between Science, Policy and Society.

EXPERT VOICES FOR YOUTH

Speaker contributions for the *Youth Goals*

SUSANA MALCORRA

CV:

The former Foreign Minister of Argentina and former Chief of Staff of Secretary-General Ban Ki-moon, decided after her time at the UN that there was a need for an organisation to highlight the importance of women in positions of power. That is why she created GWL Voices, together with other great figures, to bring together world leaders and achieve the ultimate goal of having a woman as Secretary General of the United Nations in 2026.

SUMMARY

"Analysis of the global situation: a view from women's leadership"

The talk focuses on the profound changes that the world is currently undergoing. According to Malcorra, we are experiencing an exponential transformation in existing models, characterised by an unprecedented speed that generates multiple instabilities. The speaker identifies three fundamental axes to consider in this context: geopolitics, the challenge to democracy and technological disruption.

At the macro level, he stresses that the world is facing a rebalancing of economic and geopolitical power, a rise of political illiberalism particularly in the West, and significant technological disruption. As a consequence, we are facing a new world order that is still undefined and the need for a new social contract within countries.

EXPERT VOICES FOR YOUTH

Speaker contributions for the *Youth Goals*

ELENA VALENCIANO

CV:

Elena Valenciano is a Spanish socialist politician. She has been Deputy Secretary General of the PSOE, Member of the European Parliament and Member of the Spanish Parliament. She specialises in conflict prevention, peace, reconciliation and dialogue at the Henri Dunant Centre for Humanitarian Dialogue in Geneva. Since October 2021, she chairs Fundación Mujeres, as part of her strong commitment to the feminist struggle.

SUMMARY

"European youth: disillusionment or hope for the future?"

Elena used her dialogue to present to the students of the University of Salamanca and members of civil society the current situation of young people in Europe and its geographical vicinity, in terms of mental health, employment, poverty, access to housing and other aspects. He presented, through official data from sources such as Eurostat and the European Youth Forum, the global situation of the youth population. He highlighted in the session how the work of the European Union and the battle against climate change are currently two keys to change. He highlighted data analysis as a key element for policy development and invited young people to be an active part of the processes.

EXPERT VOICES FOR YOUTH

Speaker contributions for the *Youth Goals*

SAMUEL DAVID COLINA SANTANA
ALEXIS JAKEL GÓMEZ CRESPO
SAMUEL JOSÉ ROJAS VIELMA

Students on the Degree in Political Science
University of Salamanca

SUMMARY

“How can young people have an impact on public policy?”

This presentation focused on the role of youth entrepreneurship as a way for young people to actively influence public policy. The speakers argued that encouraging start-ups with social impact, promoting financial education and facilitating access to specialised training can empower young people. They also raised the need to create alliances between universities, businesses and administrations to provide real opportunities for development. They stressed the importance of creating spaces such as entrepreneurship fairs, co-working spaces and collaborative networks, as well as promoting mentoring programmes and access to public incentives. They stressed that youth innovation and entrepreneurship should be key tools in inclusion and participation strategies.

EXPERT VOICES FOR YOUTH

Speaker contributions for the *Youth Goals*

MARTA RUIZ DE LA HERMOSA GONZÁLEZ DE LA ALEJA
SERGIO GALÁN LÓPEZ

Students on the Degree in Statistics
University of Salamanca

SUMMARY

“Why policy design and evaluation must use data and evidence”

This session highlighted the need to design and evaluate public policies for young people on the basis of reliable data and empirical evidence. The speakers clearly explained the whole evaluation process: from identifying problems to measuring impact, including setting targets and implementing monitoring systems. They stressed the importance of using official indicators, opinion polls and real-time monitoring technologies. They also presented initiatives such as Youth Guarantee Plus and Erasmus+ as examples of programmes that require continuous evaluation. They also warned against institutional resistance to the use of data and the existence of analytical biases, and called for the professionalisation of decision-making in youth affairs.

EXPERT VOICES FOR YOUTH

Speaker contributions for the *Youth Goals*

**RICARDO FERNÁNDEZ MAESTRO
ANDREA MACHUCA AULISI**

**Students on the Degree in Political Science
University of Salamanca**

SUMMARY

“What challenges do we face in implementing effective youth policies?”

With a critical and reflective approach, this presentation explored the obstacles that youth policies face in order to be truly effective. Through provocative questions such as 'do they really want to listen to us' or 'are we partly to blame', the speakers invited us to think about the lack of representation and the generation gap as structural barriers. They defended the need to create listening institutions that work in both directions, where young people have a real voice and can produce tangible results. They also pointed out that the low participation of young people in elections reduces the political influence of the youth collective. They insisted that the importance of young people cannot remain symbolic, but must be translated into concrete and sustainable decision-making structures.

INTEGRATED GUIDELINES FOR YOUTH PUBLIC POLICIES

1. Connecting the EU to young people

- Establish EU Focal Points in schools and universities.
- Facilitate face-to-face and virtual meetings with EU actors.
- Training programmes in youth diplomacy and international participation.
- Globalised civic education on current geopolitical issues.

2. Gender equality

- Implementation of zipper lists for state and regional parliaments.
- Gender quotas (40-60) in the executive, judiciary and public administration.
- Educational and cultural programmes promoting diversity, inclusion and tolerance.

3. Inclusive societies

- Civic education for 'new Europeans'.
- Programmes that integrate cultural and sexual diversity in companies, organisations and public authorities.

4. Information and constructive dialogue

- Creating and publicising spaces for social dialogue between young people and political representatives.
- Flexible mechanisms for presenting youth initiatives on public policies.
- Permanent youth consultations, forums and councils.

- Spaces for dialogue between science, politics and society:
 - ▶ Creating permanent institutions for listening to young people at local and national level.
 - ▶ Encourage two-way listening mechanisms that recognise both complaints and constructive proposals.
 - ▶ Create intergenerational spaces to reduce the generation gap and promote mutual understanding.
 - ▶ Establish stable channels of dialogue with clear accountability on the part of public authorities.
 - ▶ Encourage real participation of young people in the decision-making process.

5. Mental health and well-being:

- Disseminate information on health care in universities and schools.
- Psychologists specialising in young people in schools, universities and training centres.
- Comprehensive public programmes of psychological care for young people.
- Specific awareness and prevention campaigns.
- Periodic epidemiological studies on the mental health of young people.

6. Empowerment of rural youth

- Grants for rural youth entrepreneurship with internet connectivity.
- Adequate provision of public services in rural areas.

7. Quality employment for all

- Reduction of social security contributions for hiring young people (18-24 years).
- On-the-job training through public-private cooperation.
- Labour market integration programmes with training,

internships and active support.

- Incentives for companies to recruit young people at risk.
- Dual education and technical training tailored to the market.
- Promotion of youth entrepreneurship with social impact through mentoring, specialised training and spaces such as fairs, co-working spaces or youth hubs.
- Building alliances between businesses and universities to facilitate access to training, resources and practical experience.
- Specific strategies for youth employment in emerging sectors.

8. Quality learning

- Mandatory inclusion of second and third languages in the curriculum.
- Active listening to employers in order to adapt youth training.
- Training young people in advanced and flexible digital skills.

9. Spaces and participation for all

- Creating spaces for youth dialogue on fears, aspirations and problems.
- Summarising youth conclusions and presenting them to public authorities.
- Formal platforms for youth participation in public institutions.
- Training in civic participation and active democracy.

10. A green and sustainable Europe

- Support for green, low-carbon youth employment.
- Tax incentives and quota reductions for green youth entrepreneurship.
- Involving youth in national and local climate strategies.
- Youth-led climate education and awareness-raising.

11. European programmes and youth organisations

- Creación de asociaciones juveniles que representen grupos menos visibles (cultural, social, sexual).
- Nuevos programas europeos adaptados a inquietudes juveniles.
- Proyectos juveniles internacionales sobre migración, cambio climático, paz y seguridad.
- Visibilizar el impacto de programas como Erasmus+ en formación, participación social e identidad europea.
- Alinear las nuevas iniciativas europeas con las necesidades reales de la juventud, basándose en procesos participativos y evaluación de impacto.

Transversal: Evidence-Based Engagement

All these guidelines must be underpinned by solid and rigorous scientific evidence. It is essential to have youth observatories to collect and analyse reliable data, to promote the publication of peer-reviewed studies, to provide training in quantitative and qualitative methods for evaluating youth policies and to define clear criteria for scientific quality. It is also essential to constantly monitor for errors and bias by using control and randomisation groups, analysing confounding factors such as socio-economic status, gender or age, and conducting regular critical reviews of the youth interventions implemented.

- Design youth policies with clear data-based evaluation processes:
 - ▶ Identify priority problems.
 - ▶ Set measurable targets.
 - ▶ Allocate resources with realistic timetables.
 - ▶ Monitor in real time.
 - ▶ Adjust policies according to results.
- Promote the use of statistics and data literacy among young people.
- Include official indicators and opinion surveys in the design and review of youth policies.
- Use new technologies for data collection and analysis.
- Overcoming institutional resistance to the evidence-based approach.

YOUTH MANIFESTO FOR THE FUTURE: OUR VOICE, OUR AGENDA

What concerns us as youth? What do we need to change? What policies do we want to see? This document is a result of the open and collaborative space in which different young people composed, concerns, proposals or demands. Together they built a Youth Manifesto that gathers the voice of those who really feel what youth need: young people.

"This manifesto is the result of a collaborative construction carried out by young participants in the Youth Goals Research and Contribution project. Through an interactive virtual space (Padlet), young people shared their proposals, concerns and aspirations regarding the major challenges facing public policies aimed at youth. This space not only reflects their critical voice, but also their commitment to social transformation, equity and active participation. The manifesto is, therefore, a tool for collective expression that reflects the diversity of views of a generation that demands to be heard, taken into account and fully incorporated into the processes of design, implementation and evaluation of public policies".

INTRODUCTION

We, youth and participants of the Youth Goals Research Centre, believe in the importance of youth being heard in the design of public policy. Our voice must be backed by data, evidence and real experiences to make a meaningful impact.

BUILDING THE FUTURE TOGETHER

We believe that the most effective public policies are born from the dialogue between young people, researchers, policy makers and civil society. We need more spaces for intergenerational and multidisciplinary collaboration to find innovative and sustainable solutions to the challenges of our generation.

We are not only talking about young people, we are talking about social problems, the difficulties and concerns of a whole generation that needs to be heard.

YOUTH AND PUBLIC POLICY: A NECESSARY DIALOGUE

What we expect from public policies

- It is expected that during the educational period they will be offered work opportunities adapted to their situations and needs. Moreover, these should be focused on the long term and not remain a mere temporary and stagnant experience.
 - That they value the real needs of young people and that they are effective and materialize in everyday life.
 - That the policies have concrete goals to achieve and youth objectives so that they do not remain a declaration of intentions.
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- That they reach all young people, especially those from vulnerable families or with lower incomes, and that they serve rural areas, where there are no businesses.
 - They must be effective, relevant and fast. Public policies must also be equal for all. Finally, they must have a long-term perspective.
 - They must be as close as possible to the electoral program. There is no point in promising to come to power and then be forgotten.
 - They must be realistic, tangible and close to the people. That they do not concentrate on.

the data are quantitative, since in many cases there are people who are “invisible” and for whom no work is done, since their perspective, problems and context are not taken into consideration.

What concerns us as youth

- The need for a youth perspective of the changes that the educational system needs: who can be closer to it than the young people themselves who have just become part of this space that needs to adapt to the changes in the social reality?
 - Greater participation and representation of the European youth collective both in the decision-making institutions and the institutions that carry out the very policies aimed at youth for a direct evaluation of their evolution and their implementation by young people.
 - The youth perspective can have different dimensions. First, concern may focus on basic necessities, such as housing or food. Second, we are concerned about the evolution of society, both nationally and globally (lack of participation, political evolution, end of peace).
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- Spanish youth is very quiet. Faced with the reputation of rebelliousness of this generation: act, take sides. We must stand up by means of a useful vote, but above all by being aware of what has already happened.
 - We are concerned about youth unemployment, the difficult access to housing, the lack of opportunities, the evolution of retirement pensions, the lack of political participation, the fear of entrepreneurship.
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- We are concerned about the foreboding of a future for which we are not prepared and the responsibility to alleviate current problems, such as the pension problem.
- The socio-economic reality of the EU is in crisis, so it is important to focus first on solving the general crisis, in order to focus on the collectives, and allocate funds.
- We are concerned about: i) the information bubble that can generate information bias during our decision making; ii) the inclusion of young people in divergent spheres and when, in some occasions it happens, unfortunately there is misappropriation of funds.

the influence of social networks: Have social networks become the new drug that keeps us silent?

- The influence of social networks: Have social networks become the new drug that keeps us silent? Do we really have our own opinions today or are they a mere product of the biased content we consume?
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- As young people in both Spain and the EU, we believe that the decisions that will affect our individual and collective future as a country should not be made solely by a few elites of a consolidated age range. We believe as young people that taking into account that we are the future generations that will live in this society, we must take part of the measures and public policies, because in the end we are the ones that most affect and will affect our lives. For example, with the issue of housing and its difficult access, labor precariousness with temporary contracts and scholarship holders or European mobility with failures in its regulation. There are many examples that can be given to show that young people must take sides in decision-making and deserve to be heard.
 - Time problems. Students do not have time to take advantage of all the opportunities offered by the university and be able to evolve and improve as university students. What good is it for us that the university has programs to learn skills and train us, if we do not have time due to the intensive schedule of classes, which in 99% of cases is incompatible with, for example, conferences, lectures, panel discussions and other activities that associations and the university itself offer?

THE IMPORTANCE OF EVIDENCE

Decisions affecting youth must be based on sound data and rigorous analysis. Statistics and impact evaluation are key tools for understanding our needs and measuring the effectiveness of policies. We are committed to transparent and useful data collection to transform reality.

The role of data and evidence in policies

- To be effective, to really understand what is happening. Therefore, the use of data allows us to get closer to reality, and to elaborate policies adapted to a situation.
 - The use of statistical data with information from European youth is fundamental to achieve improvements in our welfare and so the European institutions can act appropriately
 - It is necessary to choose the most efficient public policy based on evidence, so that the (limited) resources are allocated where they generate the most results.
 - We must avoid falling into hoaxes and fake News, contrasting all the information that comes to us in a truthful and empirical way, that is why the use of statistics and data analysis is key to our future.
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- It is necessary that the data from the surveys conducted be accessible, understandable and simple for all ordinary citizens. We are not talking about numbers, but about people. We cannot turn our backs on data; they must be read and applied to design data-driven policies.
 - The European Union must legislate and force large technology companies to implement programs to detect misinformation.
 - In the absence of effective listening due to limited political participation, data can sometimes bring the needs of young people to the attention of legislators. In other words, data can speak for us.
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Ideas for a better future

Promote the most depopulated areas, villages, rural areas.

So that young people do not have to leave, job and training opportunities can be created in these villages to make these places accessible (improved transportation and connections). Also highlight the difficulties of young people for housing and forming families, in which these environments can be the solution.

Visibility and greater funding of youth entities

Both European and Spanish institutions should increase funding and give greater visibility and promotion to entities such as the Youth Council, both national and regional and provincial. At the same time, cultural associations whose content is aimed at young people should be financed. We could even consider financing youth associations linked to political parties, since they are places for the exchange of ideas and with young people interested in participating in public life.

EU Visibility and Promotion Policies

In our opinion, the EU does not make itself sufficiently known to young people. Measures should be taken to bring institutions, actions and policies closer to young people.

Create youth associations with initiative in order to reach out to current needs.

Quality education

Teachers should adapt to the new times, they cannot continue to depend so much on memory when that is a task that today a machine is capable of carrying out much more efficiently. I believe that class attendance should be much freer, encourage self-learning and that classes should be used to solve doubts, to reason in class, to have dialogues, etc. Classes cannot continue to consist of sitting in a chair and copying everything the teacher dictates, at least not if we want to advance as a society.

Increased relationship between public universities and private companies.

Industry development

Need to have its own industry that can generate stable, quality jobs for young people in order to have access to decent housing, and that the native population has easy access to jobs.

Also, this industry can have an impact on R&D&I, which has a positive impact on society.

This requires collaboration between the public and private sectors, creating synergies for the benefit of all.

Regional representation

- The autonomous community of Castilla y La Mancha in 2023, was in charge of coordinating the autonomous community representation in youth matters before the EU. This generates problems due to the fact that each autonomous community has different realities and priorities, as for example youth unemployment may be more serious in some regions than in others. For this reason, a system of regional consultations should be created prior to this representation, organizing meetings with youth representatives from each autonomous community before taking proposals to the EU.
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CLOSING

Nothing about us without us.
Young people must be part of
the change!

#YGRC: Youth Goals Research Centre (101047538)

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